

IMPORTANCE OF FORECASTING WATERING OF GAS CONDENSATE WELLS (ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE KHALISMATOV- NAZAROV-NURMUKHAMEDOV METHOD)

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ABSTRACT

One of the main problems in the development of gas condensate wells is the increasing water cut during production period. This factor significantly affects well operation modes and in the most cases does not allow achieving full drainage of gas reserves and, consequently, the planned gas and condensate recovery factors (GRF/CRF). Taking into account the indicated circumstance, there is an urgent need for an operational forecast of watering, which requires the development of a specific methodology individually for each operational facility. The main key factor in the operational forecast of watering is the express application of the results based on analysis of newly received well logging and well testing data for monitoring field development, as well as selected samples of reservoir fluids when compiling well operation parameters.

Forecasting the water cut of gas condensate wells (the main indicator of which is WGR) operating gas condensate reservoirs is carried out by the following accepted methods:

- application of a 3D hydrodynamic compositional model that takes into account changes in gas composition, relative phase permeabilities, gas supercompressibility coefficients, CGR and WGR, reservoir pressure, volume and rate of intrusion of marginal/bottom waters into productive formations, etc. [1];

- application of a 2D hydrodynamic model that takes into account the change in relative phase permeabilities and reservoir

pressure, the other above parameters are calculated using certain dependencies [2];

- application of a graph-analytical express method based on the analysis of actual indicators of development and field research, as well as plotting dependencies with the identification of a certain pattern [3, 4].

Taking into account the need to promptly obtain the results of the forecast and make a decision on further geological and technical measures, the best method, in our opinion, will be the graph-analytical express method, which is proposed to be called the Khalismatov-Nazarov-Nurmukhamedov method.

The need to develop a methodology for predicting water cut was necessitated by the results of operating production wells. In the process of analyzing the actual data, cases of a sharp increase in water cut were identified, especially, an increase in WGR (the ratio of water production to gas production) (Charts 1-5, growth areas are highlighted in red ovals). It should be noted that the transferred technological modes of operation of the wells, WGR were not predicted, and, accordingly, it was not possible to quickly influence the situation with a sharp increase in water cut.

Charts 1-4 compare the dynamics of the actual daily gas production, CGR and WGR with those adopted in wells operational parameters, but as noted, WGR was not taken into account in wells operational parameters, most likely due to the lack of a specific methodology for its prediction. As can be seen from the charts, the dynamics of actual gas production and CGR practically correspond to wells operation parameters, taking into account minor deviations, and the actual dynamics of the WGR requires the identification of patterns for its further operational forecasting.

Chart 1 - Comparison of the dynamics of daily gas production, condensate-gas and water-gas factors of fields

Chart 2 - Comparison of the dynamics of daily gas production, condensate-gas and water-gas factors for well No. 1

Graph 3—Comparison of the dynamics of daily gas production, condensate-gas and water-gas factors for well No. 2

Chart 4—Comparison of the dynamics of daily gas production, condensate-gas and water-gas factors for well No. 3

To identify this pattern, first of all, the results of wells logging for monitoring reservoirs development are needed. But, taking into consideration, that these studies were carried out very rarely, along

with the actual data on wells operation, the developed methodology for watering forecast will consider the results of wells testing and gas condensate studies, as well as the results of formation water sampling.

Conclusions

1. The need to develop a methodology for forecasting watering of gas condensate wells products has been identified.

2. The graph-analytical express method (Khalismatov-Nazarov-Nurmukhamedov method) will be adopted as the basis for the development of this methodology.

3. While developing the Khalismatov-Nazarov-Nurmukhamedov Method, the

uncertainty factor is considered, due to the limited results of well logging for monitoring production reservoirs development.

4. The result of the application of the developed methodology will be implement for operational planning of geological and technical activities in order to prevent a sharp increase in the WGR and ensure the achievement of the planned GRF and CRF.

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